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PHYSICAL MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION IN THE ACUSAT PROJECT

by

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1. INTRODUCTION

Modeling is used in the project AcuSat to better understand how biomass is being distributed by mesoscale activity and how mesoscale activity influences primary and secondary production in the Norwegian Sea. They are also used to understand the data collected during cruises and test hypothesis on how mesoscale activity influences biological production in the ocean.

AcuSat is a collaboration between NERSC and IMR who have different physical-biological modeling systems and both the model systems are used in the project. The system at IMR includes a coupling between phytoplankton and zooplankton, while at NERSC these two components are not coupled. In the first year of the project the physical models were set up and validated. Here we report on this activity. This report is a project deliverable from AcuSat WP5: Coupled biophysical modeling.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE MODEL SYSTEMS

Two model systems are used in the project. Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM: Bleck, 2002 - www.hycom.org) and the Regional Ocean Model System (ROMS: Haidvogel et al., 2008 - www.myroms.org). HYCOM uses a combination of isopycnal and z-coordinates and is set up in an area along the Norwegian Coast from Trondheim in the south to Tromsø in the north (Fig. 1). This model is nested in the TOPAZ model of the North Atlantic (<http://topaz.nersc.no>) and has a resolution of 2.3 km. The model has 28 vertical layers, of which the 5 upper layer are in z-coordinated and the lower 23 layer are hybrid layers. The model is forced by the ERA Interim forcing (Simmons et al., 2007), which is a 6-hourly reanalysis product available from 1989 to present. The river forcing is generated using a hydrological model - TRIP (Oki and Sud, 1998). Sea surface salinity is relaxed back to climatology with a relaxation timescale of 200 days, while no relaxation is applied to the sea surface temperature. Tidal forcing is applied at the lateral boundaries and is generated from the FES2004 tidal atlas (Lyard et al., 2006).

ROMS is run on a model domain covering the Nordic Seas, the North Sea, the Barents Sea, the Kara Sea and partly the Arctic (Fig. 2), and has a spatial resolution of 4 km, with 30 s-coordinates (stretched, terrain-following) in the vertical. Monthly mean lateral boundary conditions were taken from a global version of ROMS with a resolution of about 20 km in the North Atlantic and Arctic, and consist of 3D velocities, SSH, temperature and salinity. In addition, 8 tidal constituents from the Oregon State University TOPEX/Poseidon Global Inverse Solution (TPXO 7.0: Egbert et al., 1994; Egbert and Erofeeva, 2002) were added to the SSH and barotropic flow at the lateral boundaries. Six-hourly vertical boundary conditions were taken from ERA interim (www.ecmwf.int) and included sea surface air pressure, wind stress, latent, sensible, downward shortwave radiative and net longwave radiative heat flux.

Figure 1. The model domain for the HYCOM model used in AcuSat. The figure also shows the temperature distribution in the surface layer on May 10, 1999.

Figure 2. Model domain for the ROMS model, covering the Nordic Seas, the North Sea, the Barents Sea, the Kara Sea and partly the Arctic Ocean. The contour levels indicate depths and the numbers on the axis are grid cells.

3. MODEL STATUS

3.1 HYCOM

During the last year NERSC upgraded their HYCOM model to the latest version (V2.2) and a large effort was put into setting up and quality checking this model. The new version has several improvements compared to the previous version. Some of these include:

- Improved vertical interpolation algorithm, from piecewise constant to piecewise parabolic.
- Improved stability in shallow waters (Morel et al., 2008).
- Improved representation of rivers based on a global hydrological model (Oki and Sud, 1998).
- Easier inclusion of the ecosystem model, useful for the biological applications.
- The particle tracking code is now run with distributed memory parallelization (MPI).

In addition a diurnal cycle in the solar irradiance was implemented.

The nested model was initialized at the beginning of 1996 with interpolated fields from the larger model. Because the larger model was initiated in 1973, it is sufficient to spin up the nested model for one year. This model has currently been run up to 1. January 2000. The results have compared to salinity and temperature data downloads from the ICES database (<http://www.ices.dk/ocean/asp/Chem/HydChem/HydChem.aspx>). To study how passively floating matter is distributed by mesoscale activity, a few modeling experiment where passively floating particles has been released in the model domain has also been performed.

3.2 ROMS

Long simulations (1989-2008) of the Nordic Seas, ROMS has until now mostly been run with 20km resolution and model setup as described in Lien et al (2006). Some known weaknesses of this model system are known, of which too strong retroflexion of cold, fresh water in the East Greenland current and thus a eastward displacement of the Atlantic/Polar water mass front along the Norwegian Coast are of special interest to the AcuSat modeling component. When improving the resolution to 4km, several attempts to improve the retroflexion were tested (change of advection schemes, bottom topography smoothing etc), but this needs further explorations and thus the 20km setup is used for the time being.

4. MODEL RESULTS AND VALIDATION

4.1 HYCOM

There were normally between 500 and 4000 measurements per month in the ICES dataset used for model comparison. The measurements were more numerous and spread over a larger area in the summer months. The measurements in the winter months tended to be concentrated along the coast. During 1997 and 1998 there were measurement down to 2000 meters on a regular basis at Ocean Weather Station Mike (2 °E, 66 °W), this was very useful for evaluating the deeper water masses in the model. As seen in Figure 1 there is quite a bit of mesoscale variability in the model. Validation with point measurements is therefore problematic, because we expect large variability over relatively short distances, but we don't expect the model to be able to place the mesoscale variability in the correct place. Figure 3 shows an example of a point-to-point comparison in the upper layers of the model.

At Station M the temperatures at the surface and below 100 meters are well simulated, but at mid-levels between 500 and 1000 the model is too warm and too saline (Figure 4). When studying individual profiles it becomes clear that the main thermocline between Atlantic Water and the colder fresher water masses below are too diffuse. This diffusion of

the thermocline occurs in several models (Ferry et al., 2007; Gruber et al., 2006), however, this weakness is thought to be particularly pronounced in HYCOM as additional mixing is generated during the remapping of the vertical coordinates at the interface between the z-coordinates and isopycnal coordinates (Griffies et al., 2009).

Figure 3. Comparison between data sampled on April 30 1999 and the daily average model field for that day. The temperature (upper 6 panels) is realistic, while the salinity (lower 6 panels) of the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) is too saline. The front between the NCC and Norwegian Atlantic Current (NwAC) seems to be sharper in the data and more diffuse over the shelf break in the model. The shelf break is indicated by the black line on the figure, which is the 500-meter isobath.

Figure 4. Modeled (red) and observed (blue) temperatures at 3 different depth intervals at station M in 1997.

We did not have access to any current measurements for the validation of the model. We checked that the currents were consistent with expected patterns in the area and that the transports in the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) and Norwegian Atlantic Current (NwAC) are reasonable. The NCC follows the coast and has an annual mean transport of 0.86 Sv in the southern part of the domain and 0.95 Sv in the northern part of the domain. The NCC transport is largest in the winter (>1 Sv) and about 0.6-0.7 Sv in the summer. Björk (2001) estimate the NCC transport to be 0.7 Sv based on hydrographic measurements. The NwAC is broadening over the Vøringen Plateau (Fig. 5) which is a well know feature of the Norwegian Sea circulation. As a proxy for transport of Atlantic water in the model we calculated the transport of water with salinity > 35 . The transport is 4.5 Sv in the southern part of the domain and 4.0 in the northern part of the domain. This transport is also largest in winter and smallest during summer which is consistent with observations (Orvik et al., 2001). An eddy is seen in figure 5, this eddy was spun off the NCC and is slowly drifting southwest toward the deepest part of the Lofoten basin. A similar feature is described in (Kohl, 2007) and is though to be a central mechanism in the deepening of the mixed layer in the Lofoten basin (Rossby et al., 2009)

Figure 5. The mean currents and salinity in March of 1999.

4.2 ROMS

The model system has been validated and used for impact studies of inter-annual variation in physical forcing on northward displacement and temperature exposure of Norwegian spring spawning herring larvae (*Clupea harengus*) in Vikebø et al. (2009), and some of their findings on model representativeness will be repeated here.

The simulations reproduce well-known features of the hydrography and circulation in the Svinøy-section (0°E, 65°N to 5°E 62.3°N) as described by Orvik et al. (2001) and Orvik and Skagseth (2005). The section is dominated by the relatively warm and saline NASC, which constitutes the eastern branch of the NwAC, trapped along the shelf edge, with the slightly cooler and fresher wedge-shaped NCC on the shelf (Fig 6). The NASC is seen as a strong, northward flowing current over the shelf break, with a sub-surface temperature and salinity maximum. The slopes of the isohalines at the interface between NCC and NASC are tilted more in March than in June indicating a seasonal weakening in the NCC. At the same time the NCC becomes warmer, increasing from less than 6 °C in March to more than 10°C in June.

Modeled annual mean volume flux of NASC (defined by temperatures above 5°C and salinity above 35 psu) for the period 1997 to 1999 (overlapping with measurements in Orvik et al. 2001) is 4.6 Sv, while the measurements indicated 4.2 Sv. There is a strong seasonal signal in the volume transport with maximum in winter and minimum in early summer, consistent with observations. In addition, the winter maximum and summer minimum is comparable to observations. The second peak in volume flux during fall, as can be seen in the measurements, is captured by the model but somewhat overestimated. Fig. 7 shows monthly averaged velocities at 20 m along with temperatures for March and April 1989-2008 and correspondingly only for 1997. Several interesting features appear in these panels. We can see the eddy structures along the shelf break occurring in the NASC as reported by Rossby et al. (2009) using Rafos floats and Orvik et al. (2001) using vessel mounted ADCP. The 1989-

2008 averages indicate that these eddy structures are not persistent and that their locations may vary in time. On the shelf the core of the NCC is cooler than farther off the coast. The main inner drift route goes along the 200 m isoline as reported in Sætre (1999), with less unidirectional flow above the bank structures as can be seen from drift experiments. The distance between the core of the NCC and the coastline increases when approaching the Vestfjord, leaving a progressively increasing area of waters with enhanced retention (Fig. 7).

Figure 6. Simulated data from the Svinøy cross section used for model validation: Average salinity for March (a) and June (b) and temperature for March (c) and June (d) over the entire model period 1989-2008.

Figure 7. Simulated monthly mean circulation and temperature at 20 m depth averaged over every month of March 1989-2008 (a) and for March (c) and April (d) 1997

5. NEXT STEPS

In the next period the HYCOM will be run up to present date and the development of the 4-km ROMS model will continue. When these runs are finished a comparison to the observations from the AcuSat cruises in 2009 will be performed. During the next year both models will be run coupled to the biological models and the results will be validated with respect to the biological results. The runs with particle distributions will be analyzed and simulations will also be performed in connection to cruise activity.

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